

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the methodology of language teaching and the use of modern technologies in language teaching.*

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Today, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. Several English language experts are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This will certainly increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. There are several unique advantages of teaching using technologies. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and move forward. Technology is slowly replacing traditional teaching methods. is taking its place. [1]Today, a number of new programs and shows that help to teach the English language are regularly broadcast on television programs. It should also be noted that today there is a new trend of using new modern innovative technologies in Uzbekistan to increase the effectiveness of teaching. methods were introduced. For example, a student who is being taught a foreign language on the basis of multimedia had the opportunity to develop four skills and learn through interesting materials both by sight and hearing. In addition, the student can guess the meaning of some words by watching live actions and tries to understand it. [2]It allows the young generation to learn foreign languages faster. Some teachers do not know how to apply and do not use technologies during English classes, which causes some boredom of students. It is for this reason that in order not to extinguish the enthusiasm of the learner, the use of technology and at least the computer during the lesson ensures that the interest of the learner increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective.[3]

On the contrary, if we teachers do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast video films, songs or texts containing complex words to elementary school students, or if we show them through multimedia, computers, When we present teaching materials with very simple texts to elementary and high school students or groups, the students' interest in learning the language gradually fades and they don't master the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to a drop in grades and a loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students. So, it follows that the main task is not just to use technologies during the lesson, but to be able to use them in their place and to ensure that the use of technologies serves to increase the student's

knowledge. According to the requirements of the current CEFR, i.e. International European Education Standards, the four competences of learning in English: (writing, reading, listening, speaking) are conducted. effective and appropriate use of technologies during lessons is important. For example, listening comprehension lessons have their own rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material he is listening to and be able to analyze it without difficulty. For this, the first thing is to prepare the environment for playing the audio material, in which the listeners provide a quiet environment, and the teacher focuses on the quality of the audio being played and that the sound amplifiers are working well, and the exercises to be performed before and after the audio are played. ready and students should be provided with handouts. After all the requirements are fulfilled, the teacher can start broadcasting the audio material to the students. Listening is done at least twice, otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to perform the exercises correctly after listening to the audio material.[4]

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; — it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

It is also a very effective way to show students videos, clips, and discuss them using multimedia in the process of teaching using technology in speaking and writing. It is possible to use the vocabulary familiar to the learners, to explain the words if there are new and complex words, and after completing the exercises related to the new words, it is possible to show the video material. . In order to carry out this process, it is important to have a quiet, noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, the possibility of watching for everyone, and checking that the loudspeakers are working. Before posting the video, the students should discuss the topic of the video to be shown, conduct a question and answer session, and after making sure that the students are really interested in the topic, the video material should be posted. When the video is over, the teacher should be interested in the students' thoughts about the video and do exercises. When these stages are properly implemented, these lessons will definitely contribute to the growth of students' interests and knowledge. It follows from this that the role of modern technologies in enriching our lessons, interesting students, enriching their knowledge is incomparable. Being able to use them correctly and appropriately is the main guarantee of our success.

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